

Level of Anxiety among Unsuccessful Students Undergoing Supplementary Examination

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ABSTRACT

Anxiety is something we all experience from time to time. Most people can relate to feeling tense, uncertain and, perhaps, fearful at the thought of sitting an exam, going into hospital, attending an interview or starting a new job. Students may worry about feeling uncomfortable, appearing foolish or how successful they will be. In turn, these worries can affect students sleep, appetite and ability to concentrate. If everything goes well, the anxiety will go away. This type of short-term anxiety can be useful. Feeling nervous before an exam can make us feel more alert, and enhance our performance. The main aim of the study was to assess and compare the level of anxiety among unsuccessful students before and after supplementary examination. The non-experimental research approach was adopted for the study with descriptive and comparative design. 115 students were selected by using convenience sampling technique. The tool developed and used for data collection were structured questionnaire. Paper pencil technique was used to collect data. The data obtained were analyzed by using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Result revealed that the mean percentage of anxiety scores of unsuccessful students before supplementary examination (39.84) was significantly higher than mean anxiety score after supplementary examination (29.21) as assessed by State Trait Anxiety Inventory. The mean percentage of anxiety score of unsuccessful students before supplementary examination (13.46) was significantly higher than mean anxiety score of after supplementary examination (4.84) as assessed by Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale.

KEYWORDS: Anxiety, Unsuccessful students, Supplementary examination

I. INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is something we all experience from time to time. Most people can relate to feeling tense, uncertain and, perhaps, fearful at the thought of sitting an exam, going into hospital, attending an interview or starting a new job. Students may worry about feeling uncomfortable, appearing foolish or how successful they will be. In turn, these worries can affect students sleep, appetite and ability to concentrate. If everything goes well, the anxiety will go away. This type of short-term anxiety can be useful. Feeling nervous before an exam can make us feel more alert, and enhance our performance.

Anxiety refers to student's anxiousness or worry and decrease performance or failure in examination. Anxiety disorders affect millions of adults every year, and anxiety levels among college students have been rising since the 1950s. In 2000, 7% of college students reported experiencing anxiety disorders within the previous year. Women are five times as likely to have anxiety disorders.

According to the American College Health Association's 2006 survey of college students, the one greatest health obstacle to college students' academic performance was academic stress. Of the 97,357 college students who participated in the

survey, 32 percent reported that academic stress had resulted in either an incomplete, a dropped course or a lower grade. Academic stress can be the ultimate career stopper. The key to avoid becoming a drop-out, as a result of academic stress, is to identify and treat its source.

1.1. Need of the study:-

Anxiety disorder affects million of adults every year, and anxiety levels among college students have been rising since the 1950s. In 2000, 7% of college students reported experiencing anxiety disorders within the previous year.

It is not uncommon to feel anxious about exams. Some anxiety before and during an exam can actually help enhance students performance. The extra adrenalin that stresses releases can assist the students in responding to demanding situations. Sometimes though, too much adrenalin is released and students may begin to experience fear and excessive anxiety. When this happens, student's anxiety can get in the way of the doing best. In order to keep students anxiety at a level that allows students to perform best, it is helpful to learn to respond to student's anxiety in ways that help you better manage it.

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According to national statistics, student stress stems mainly from four areas—academics, family issues, finances, and relationships. But faculty, staff, and students are more alert to the signs of depression, anxiety, or other mental health problems. These include declining grades, isolation from friends and family, inability to concentrate, eating or sleeping excessively or not enough, risky sexual behaviors, and alcohol and drug use

An estimate is that between 25% and 40% of students experience test anxiety. Further more students with disability appear to be particularly vulnerable to test anxiety and have high prevalence rate. Test anxiety decreases academic performance. High achievers expel lower levels of test anxiety and low achievers experience high levels of anxiety. There is a significant relationship between increased test anxiety and lower performance. A fraction of researches also explored that there is no relation in test anxiety and academic performance.

1.2. Statement of the problem:-

A study to assess the level of anxiety among unsuccessful students undergoing supplementary examination of selected college of nursing, Ambala, Haryana.

1.3. Objectives:-

- To assess and compare the level of anxiety among unsuccessful students before and after supplementary examination.

1.4. Assumptions:-

- Unsuccessful students may have some level of anxiety before the supplementary examination.
- Samples are the true representation of population.

1.5. Delimitation:-

- Only one setting.
- Unsuccessful students of selected college of nursing.

II. METHODOLOGY

In view of the nature of the problem & to accomplish the objectives of the study, Quantitative - Non experimental research approach was used in present study. The research design used in this study was Descriptive and Comparative research design. The study was conducted at M.M. College Of Nursing, Mullana, Ambala. The sample was 115 unsuccessful students undergoing supplementary examination were selected by using convenience sampling technique. the tools used for the study was Section A description of demographic characteristics of the study participants (age, gender, academic year, religion, type of family, total family income, percentage of previous academic performance, failed in number of subjects, support system available, use of coping mechanism), Section B State-trait anxiety inventory (The State Trait Anxiety Inventory evaluates feelings of apprehension, tension, nervousness, worry, which increase in response to physical danger and psychological stress. The inventory contains 40 items with a 4-point rating scale) Section C Hamilton anxiety rating scale (. The scale consist of 14 items, each defined by a series of symptoms, and measure both psychic anxiety and somatic anxiety). Each item is scored on a scale of 0 (not present) to 4 (severe), with a total score range of 0-56, where <17 indicates mild anxiety, 18-24 moderate anxiety and >24 severe anxiety) The content validity of tools was done by submitting the tools 7 experts from the field of Medical Surgical Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing , Paediatric Nursing and Obstetrical Nursing. The internal consistency of State Trait Anxiety Inventory was found to be 0.86 and for Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale it was found to be 0.77

III. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Demographic Variables among Unsuccessful Students N=115

S. No	Socio demographic variables	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age		
	a) 17-19 years	27	23.48
	b) 20-22 years	68	59.13
	c) 23-24 years	19	16.52
	d) ≥ 25 years	01	0.87
2.	Gender		
	a) Male	27	23.48
	b) Female	88	76.52
3.	Academic Year		
	a) B.sc(N)2 nd yr	39	33.91
	b) B.sc(N)3 rd yr	48	41.74
	c) B.sc(N)4 th yr	19	16.52
	d) P.B.B.sc(N)2 nd yr	09	7.83
4.	Type of family		
	a) Nuclear family	83	72.17
	b) Joint family	32	27.83
5.	Total family income		
	a) <5000	07	6.09
	b) 5001-10000	12	10.43
	c) 10001-15000	42	36.52
	d) >15001	54	46.96
6.	Percentage of previous academic performance		
	a) 40-50%	10	8.70
	b) 51-60%	43	37.39
	c) 61-70%	50	43.48
	d) >70%	12	10.43

7.	Failed in number of subjects		
	a) One	51	44.35
	b) Two	25	21.74
	c) Three	15	13.04
	d) More than three	24	20.87

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO. 3.1

Most of the participants (59.13%) were in age group of 20-22 years. Majority of the participants (76.52%) were females. Most of the participants (41.74%) were the students of 3rd year. Most of the participants (72.17%) belonged to Nuclear Family. Most of the participants (46.96%) have more than 15001 total family income per month. Most of the participants (43.48%) have 61-70% percentage of previous academic year. Most of the participants (44.35%) have failed in 1 subject.

3.2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Level Of Anxiety Among Unsuccessful Students Before And After Supplementary Examination As Assessed By State Trait Anxiety Inventory. N=115

Level of anxiety	Range of scores	Before examination		After examination	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Mild anxiety	20-40	28	24.34	104	90.43
Moderate anxiety	41-60	82	71.30	11	9.57
Severe anxiety	61-80	05	4.34	0	00

Minimum Score: 20
Maximum Score: 80

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO. 3.2

Table 3.2 indicates that majority 82 subjects (71.30%) were having moderate anxiety before supplementary examination whereas majority 104 subjects (90.43%) after supplementary examination.

3.3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Level of Anxiety Among Unsuccessful Students Before and After Supplementary Examination as Assessed by Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale. N=115

Level of anxiety	Range of scores	Before examination		After examination	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
No anxiety	0-13	61	53.04	112	97.4
Mild anxiety	14-17	08	6.96	2	1.74
Moderate anxiety	18-24	25	21.74	0	0
Severe anxiety	≥25	21	18.26	1	0.87

Minimum Score: 0
Maximum Score: 56

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO. 3.3

Finding in table 3.3 indicated that majority 61subjects (53.04%) were having no anxiety, 08 subjects (6.96%) were having mild anxiety, 25 subjects (21.74%) were having moderate anxiety and 21 subjects (18.26%) were having severe anxiety before supplementary examination whereas 112 subjects (97.40%) were having no anxiety, 2 subjects (1.74%) were having mild anxiety, no subject (00%) was having moderate anxiety 01 subject (0.87%) were having severe anxiety and after supplementary examination.

3.4. Range, Mean, and Mean %, Median, Standard Deviation of Anxiety Scores of Unsuccessful Students Before and After Supplementary Examination as Assessed by State Trait Anxiety Inventory N=115

	Range	Mean	Mean %	Median	Standard deviation
Before examination	27-64	45.82	39.84	45	±9.81
After examination	25-53	33.60	29.21	32	±5.10

Minimum Score = 20
Maximum Score = 80

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO. 3.4

The data presented in table 3.4 indicated that the mean anxiety score of unsuccessful students before supplementary examination (45.82 ±9.81) was higher than mean anxiety score after supplementary examination (33.60 ±5.10). It revealed that unsuccessful students have more anxiety before supplementary examination as compared to after supplementary examination.

3.5. Range, Mean, and Mean %, Median, Standard Deviation of Anxiety Scores of Unsuccessful Students Before and After Supplementary Examination as Assessed By Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale. N=115

	Range	Mean	Mean %	Median	Standard deviation
Before examination	0-41	15.48	13.46	12	±9.81
After examination	2-30	7.51	4.84	08	±3.29

Minimum Score = 00
Maximum Score = 56

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO. 3.5

The data presented in table indicated that the mean anxiety score of unsuccessful students before supplementary examination (15.48 ±9.81) was higher than mean anxiety score of after supplementary examination (7.51 ±3.29). It revealed that students have more anxiety before supplementary examination as compared to after supplementary examination.

3.6. Mean, Mean Difference, Standard Deviation of Difference, Standard Error of Mean Difference and ‘Z’ Value of Anxiety Scores of Unsuccessful Students Before and After Supplementary Examination as Assessed by STAI. N=115

	Range	Mean	Mean _D	SD _D	S.E _{MD}	Z-value
Before examination	27-64	45.82	12.22	± 2.5	0.85	14.38*
After examination	25-53	33.60				

Minimum Score = 20

Maximum Score = 80

Z (114) =1.96 p≤0.05 level of significance

*significant

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO. 3.6

The data presented in table 3.6 indicated that ‘Z’ value (14.38) for df (114) was significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there was significant difference between the anxiety scores of unsuccessful students before and after supplementary examination. Thus, it was established that the difference obtained in anxiety scores of unsuccessful students before and after supplementary examination was a true difference and not by chance.

3.7. Mean , Mean Difference, Standard Deviation of Difference, Standard Error of Mean Difference and ‘Z’ value of Anxiety Scores of Unsuccessful Students Before and After Supplementary Examination as Assessed by HAM-A. N=115

	Range	Mean	Mean _D	SD _D	S.E _{MD}	Z-value
Before examination	0-41	15.49	7.98	± 6.53	0.96	8.31*
After examination	2-30	7.51				

Minimum Score = 00

Maximum Score = 56

Z (114) =1.96 p≤0.05 level of significance

*significant

DESCRIPTON OF TABLE NO. 3.7

The data presented in table 11 indicated that ‘Z’ value (8.31) for df (114) was significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there was significant difference between the anxiety scores of unsuccessful students before and after supplementary examination. Thus, it was established that the difference obtained in anxiety scores of unsuccessful students before and after supplementary examination was a true difference and not by chance

IV. NURSING IMPLICATIONS

NURSING EDUCATION:-

- Nursing student can conduct community outreach programs to educate the students about healthy coping strategies in a community setting.
- Nursing students can be provided with opportunities for learning experiences in planning and organizing community outreach programs regarding positive coping strategies in anxiety. This includes setting specific goals, time management, analysis of various question formats, and creating a feedback system.

NURSING PRACTICE:-

- The people in the community have demanded nurses with new skills and new ways of working to face the new challenges. The community health nurse should be able to identify the children in community with increased anxiety level during exams.
- The nurse can involve mass media in increasing awareness regarding anxiety of students among parents and teachers. She should approach education and health leaders in order to formulate policies to provide special concern to these students.

NURSING RESEARCH:-

- There is a need for research in the area of anxiety among students to develop better methods in teaching, better practice in nursing care and effective teaching material. New knowledge has to be developed to create new skills and capabilities in nurses to deal with these students. Nursing research should be directed to further assess level of anxiety.

V. CONCLUSION:-

Study concluded that there was significant difference in anxiety level before and after supplementary examination among unsuccessful students as assessed by State Trait Anxiety Inventory and Hamilton Anxiety Scale.

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